

THE INFLUENCE OF MURABAHAH, MUDHARABAH, AND MUSYARAKAH INCOME ON NET RETURNS WITH FIRM SIZE AS A MODERATING VARIABLE IN ISLAMIC BANKING IN INDONESIA PERIOD 2018.Q1 - 2023.Q3

Zahro Nur Latifah, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia

Corresponding author: azizaflora45@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah are some of the common products offered by Islamic banking. Murabahah income or profit is obtained from the sale of an asset by setting a price higher than the purchase price, while Mudharabah and Musyarakah income or profit is obtained from a cooperative relationship between two or more people as the party who owns the capital and the party who manages the capital by sharing profits and losses. Although they have different working mechanisms, the three aims are to increase revenue and the size of the company. Therefore, this study analyzed the effect of the revenues of Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah on net income (NI) with the size of the company in Indonesian Islamic banks for 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. In this study, five Islamic banks were used as samples. The data are obtained from the financial statements of relevant banks and financial reports issued by the Financial Services Authority (OJK). The purpose-oriented sampling technique and multivariate regression analysis are used as data management methods. With respect to data analysis methods, Panel data regression models and moderate regression analysis methods (MRA) are used. The final results of this study show that the incomes of Murabahah and Musyarakah affect net income and the size of the company, while the incomes of Mudharabaha affect little net income and the size of the company.

Keywords: *Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, Musyarakah Income, Net Return (NI), Firm Size*

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the Sharia Banking industry continues to experience growth or improvement. Moreover, after the passing of the law containing Sharia Banking which was published on July 16 2008, namely Law No. 21 of 2008. With the issuance of this law, the growth of sharia banking in Indonesia can develop more quickly

(Susyanti, 2016). In its development, Islamic banks have also recorded quite rapid growth in the last few years. As happened in the 2016-2021 period, Sharia Banking has recorded quite impressive developments, with average asset growth of more than 65% per year (Tuzzuhro et al., 2023). Meanwhile, in the latest sharia banking statistics report issued by the Financial Services Authority (OJK), sharia banking recorded around Rp. 861.5 Trillion consisting of Sharia General Funds (BUS) & Sharia Business Units (UUS). (Otoritas Jasa Keuangan (OJK), 2024). This is certainly progress for sharia banking. The increase in interest rates set by Bank Indonesia (BI) also provides an opportunity for sharia banking to compete with conventional banking. Reporting from CNBC Indonesia, Bank Indonesia (BI) has raised its benchmark interest rate or BI rate to 6.25% in April 2024. This certainly has an impact on financing deposits or credit provided by conventional banking to the public or customers (Aprilia, 2024). Meanwhile, in sharia banking, this does not have much of an impact on companies, because basically sharia banking does not depend on or does not apply interest in its system. For this reason, sharia banking has the opportunity to continue to develop and compete with conventional banking in the future.

Even though sharia banking has quite a big opportunity in market competition in Indonesia, they must also maintain the stability of their financial performance, considering the current instability in the global economy. That's why sharia banking must really maintain its financial performance so that it remains stable and take anticipation to reduce the impact of the risk of losses that could occur at any time. One way that sharia banking can do is increase the value of the Net Return ratio (NI) and company size (Firm Size). The Net Return Ratio (NI) is an important ratio for sharia banking. This ratio can show how effective and capable the bank is in obtaining income through the placement of its productive assets in the form of financing (Khumairoh, 2018). Meanwhile, company size or firm size is a scale that measures the size of a company. In general, companies that are larger have greater guarantees than companies that are smaller, thereby reducing the level of uncertainty about the company's potential in the future (Susanti et al., 2023).

From the explanation above, it can be seen that the Net Return ratio (NI) and Firm Size can be influenced by the amount of income received by sharia banking. Unlike conventional banking where the income is obtained through interest, in sharia banking the income is obtained through the principle of profit sharing. Profit sharing is an activity where the bank and customers share profits and risks, with an agreement to share profits and losses made at the beginning of the transaction or collaboration. This profit sharing has provided benefits for banks and customers or the community, because with this principle the bank and customers or community benefit fairly. This shows an emphasis on Islamic values such as fairness in transactions, ethics in investment, growing values of brotherhood and togetherness in business activities, as well as avoiding speculative activities or guesswork in carrying out financial transactions (Priyadi & Sutardi, 2018). Some products or contracts that are based on profit sharing include Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah contracts.

These agreements have also made sharia banking more developed into a banking system option that is considered more credible and accessible and easy to

access for all Indonesian people (Susyanti, 2016). The income generated from these contracts also encourages Sharia Banking to grow and develop its business. With this growth and development, it is hoped that Sharia Banking can compete with Conventional Banking, which is generally known and widely used by the Indonesian people. (Zaenudin, 2015).

In SAK ETAP (Financial Accounting Standards for Entities Without Public Accountability), it is stated that the definition of income is a profit resulting from a company's business activities or activities, such as sales, dividends, rewards, royalties, interest and rent (Ikatan Akuntan Indonesia, 2019). Meanwhile, Harnanto (2019) explaining the definition of income is: "an increase or increase in assets and a decrease or decrease in a company's liabilities which is a result of operational activities or the procurement of goods and services to the public or consumers in particular."

So, in conclusion, income is the value or results obtained from the sale of goods or services to consumers or customers obtained in a business activity, with the aim of increasing the value of assets and fulfilling obligations by providing goods or services to the public or consumers.

So income in sharia banking is the result of contracts offered by banks. These contracts have different activities, such as Murabahah income comes from the sale of goods or services with an added fee (markup) which will be received in the form of profit. Meanwhile, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income comes from bank investments in other businesses, such as investment in the capital market, investment in the commodity market, or investment in the gold market. Meanwhile, in terms of contracts, each has a different definition or meaning and function (Susyanti, 2016).

From the previous discussion, it can be seen that each contract has different functions and activities. Apart from that, the three of them also experienced different growth. For further clarity, the following is data on the growth of Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income in Sharia Banking in Indonesia from 2018 to 2023.

Table 1
Data on the growth of Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah Sharia Banking revenues in Indonesia from 2018 to 2023 (in billions)

Contract	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Murabaha	104,847	111.114	109,150	118.204	126,735	144.128
Mudharabah	4,841	3,883	3,442	2,810	2,300	2,314
Musharakah	34,453	40,962	46,136	46,763	50,969	65,839

Source: OJK annual SPS (Data managed by the author)

The data above was obtained through the official website of the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which explains related to Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income and many income from other banking contracts. However, this research only requires data as above. From the table above, Murabahah income continued to experience an increase in income from 2018 to 2019 and then experienced a decline in 2020 with total income being IDR. 109,150 M, where in the previous year

(2019) the income generated was recorded at Rp. 111,114 M. However, even though there was a decline, the amount of Murabahah income in 2021 increased again to Rp. 118,204 M. Meanwhile, Mudharabah Income has recorded a decrease in income from 2018 to 2022, and in 2023 there has only been an increase in income, recording income of Rp. 2,314 M, which in 2022 will only record income of IDR. 2,300 M. Meanwhile, Musyarakah Income continues to experience an increase in income from 2018-2023.

This data will then be calculated and added up into several more detailed calculations, one of which is to measure a bank's performance (Net Return ratio) and how large a bank's scale is (Firm Size). Net Returns (NI) and firm size are both influenced by the income generated by a bank. To find out more about the influence of income on Net Returns (NI) and firm size, it is necessary to carry out research on this matter. From the background above, the writer became interested in conducting research on this influence.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Murabaha Income

Murabahah is one of the products offered by Sharia Banking in the form of financing. In a murabahah contract, the seller and buyer agree on the original price of the goods or services, as well as an additional fee called a margin (Setyaji & Musaroh, 2018). These additional costs do not include interest, because these additional costs are known and agreed upon at the beginning of the agreement by each party (seller and buyer). So that the Murabahah contract does not violate the provisions of Islamic Sharia. Murabahah income can be recognized when the delivery of goods is carried out directly (cash) or in stages (installments) within a period of no more than one year or can also be adjusted to the agreed term of the contract (Istikomah, 2014).

Since Law no. 10 of 1998, the Murabahah scheme has been used. This law was issued to replace the previous law, namely Law no. 7 of 1992 and paved the way for the emergence of sharia banking in Indonesia. This murabahah income has even become one of the main sources of income for sharia banking, because it is classified as short-term financing and is easy to implement. Murabahah income can be generated through various types of transactions, such as financing the purchase of goods or services, financing the purchase of land, financing the purchase of vehicles, and financing the purchase of machinery and equipment. In financing transactions for the purchase of goods or services, Islamic banks will sell goods or services at the original price plus a markup which will be received in the form of profit. Murabahah income can improve the performance of Islamic banks. (Susyanti, 2016)

Mudharabah Income

Mudharabah is a contractual agreement involving a party providing capital (shahibul mal) and another party as a manager (mudharib) who provides expertise or labor to generate profits. From these profits, the capital provider (shahibul mal) receives a predetermined rate of return, known as the profit sharing ratio, and the other party (capital manager/ mudharib) receives the remaining profits. As long as the loss is not caused by the negligence of the capital manager, the capital owner is responsible for

the loss. This agreement is commonly used in Islamic finance, because it is in line with the principles of profit *sharing* and risk sharing *which* are the core of Islamic economic theory. (Susyanti, 2016).

Mudharabah contracts are divided into two types, the first is Mudharabah Muthlaqah, namely a contract in which the shahibul mal gives the mudharib full freedom to manage his investment funds. The second is Mudharabah Muqayyadah, namely an agreement in which the shahibul mal gives restrictions to the mudharib to manage his investment funds, including restrictions regarding location, methods, investment objects, etc. (Priyadi & Sutardi, 2018). So the difference between the two lies in the management of funds.

Musharaka Income

Musyarakah is a form of cooperation involving two or more people who both contribute goods or services as capital to run a business or business. From this business, the profits *and* losses obtained *will* be shared fairly according to the portion of capital owned by both parties (Susyanti, 2016). Musyarakah is divided into 3, namely Musyarakah Muthlaqah, Musyarakah Mutanaqisah, and Musyarakah Mufawadah. Musyarakah Muthlaqah is a type of musyarakah contract where all parties have equal rights to manage the business. There is no special division of tasks, and every decision is guaranteed. Meanwhile, musyarakah mutanaqisah is a type of flexible musyarakah contract usually used in housing finance where one party, usually the capital owner, can sell part or all of its ownership to another party in stages. Meanwhile, in Musyarakah Mufawadhah, each party must contribute the same capital and all profits and losses are borne jointly. This is the simplest and fairest form of musyarakah contract (Priyadi & Sutardi, 2018).

Musyarakah income is determined based on the distribution portion according to the agreement between both parties entering into the contract, usually in the form of sharing profits obtained or generated from the jointly managed business (Istikomah, 2014). This means that the profits from this contract will be distributed according to the share of capital issued or deposited by each party.

Net Rewards (NI)

In sharia banking, Net Income (NI) is a ratio used to assess or view the performance of banking management in managing and managing all productive assets it owns with the aim of obtaining net profit. In other words, a higher NI value indicates better bank performance in generating profits. For this reason, this ratio is considered a very important indicator for the government, customers and investors. (Tiyas, 2020).

The Net Rewards Ratio is obtained from *the reduction between Fund distribution income after sharing profits with rewards and bonuses is then divided by the average total productive assets.*

$$NI = \frac{\text{Pendapatan Penyaluran Dana setelah Bagi Hasil} - (\text{Imbalan} - \text{Bonus})}{\text{Rata - rata Aktiva Produktif}}$$

Fund Distribution Income After Profit Sharing is annualized fund distribution income which has been reduced by profit sharing expenses. This income comes from fund distribution products in sharia banking, including Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah. Then this income will be further reduced by rewards and bonuses. Meanwhile, Average Total Productive Assets is a calculation of total productive assets that uses the average productive assets throughout the year.

In conventional banking, this ratio is also known as Net Interest Margin (NIM). The difference between Net Returns (NI) and Net Interest Margin (NIM) lies in the use of interest in calculating the Net Interest Margin (NIM) ratio. Interest Margin is the difference between interest costs from all funds used and interest income from all bank assets. This is of course very contrary to Islamic sharia which prohibits flowers. So Net Return (NI) and Net Interest Margin (NIM) have different calculations (Banking Smart System, 2023). Bank Indonesia (BI) also sets the standard that applies in Indonesia for the NIM/NI ratio, namely 6% (Khumairoh, 2018). The higher the NIM/NI value, the more effective and better banking performance is considered, whereas if the NIM/NI value is <6%, the bank is considered less effective in generating profits from the management of its productive assets.

Firm Size (Company size)

According to Brigham & J.F. Houston (2010), Firm Size or company size is a scale that measures the size of a company and can be classified based on total income, total assets and total equity. This method is used to determine company size. Meanwhile Hartono (2008), according to Firm Size or company size, it can be measured based on the company's total assets or assets using the calculation of the logarithmic value of total assets to determine how big or small a company is. So in conclusion, Firm Size functions to assess the company's economic performance, identify the factors that lead to the structure that causes growth, and identify the influence of company size on the company's economic performance. Apart from that, Batari Ayunda Praja & Hartono (2018) the amount of profit obtained by a company influences the size of the company (firm size). This means that if the company makes large profits or benefits so that the assets owned by the company are also large, then the size of the company (firm size) will also be larger.

Effect of Murabahah Income on Net Returns (NI) (H1)

To find out how well banking productive assets can generate profits, it is necessary to calculate the Net Return ratio. The net reward ratio (NI) is calculated by subtracting the income from disbursement of funds after sharing the profits with rewards and bonuses, then dividing by the average productive assets. More specifically, the income obtained by banks from the distribution of funds is annualized which has been reduced by profit sharing expenses, rewards and bonuses.

One of the revenues from this fund distribution comes from the Murabahah form of fund distribution products. So it can be concluded that Murabahah income obtained by sharia banks has an influence on Net Returns (NI). Apart from that, the amount of income obtained by Islamic banks also influences profit growth, where the

higher the Net Return Ratio (NI) value, the greater or higher the profit the bank will receive.

The statement above is in line with previous studies by Jati (2018), Tiyas (2020), and Awintasari & Nurhidayati (2021) which stated that the income earned by Islamic banks can influence Net Returns. From several previous studies, it is known that there is an influence between the income generated by Sharia Banking and Net Returns. However, the income referred to here is Sharia Banking income as a whole. So the specifics regarding the influence of Murabahah Income on Net Returns are not yet known.

Effect of Mudharabah Income on Net Returns (NI) (H2)

Fund distribution income can also come from fund distribution products in the form of Mudharabah. So it can be concluded that Mudharabah income obtained by sharia banks also has an influence on Net Returns (NI).

This statement is also in line with studies that have been carried out previously Jati (2018), Tiyas (2020) and Awintasari & Nurhidayati (2021) which state that the income earned by Islamic banks can influence Net Returns. From several previous studies, it is known that there is an influence between the income generated by Sharia Banking and Net Returns. However, the income referred to here is Sharia Banking income as a whole. So it is not yet known specifically about the influence of Mudharabah Income on Net Returns.

The Effect of Musyarakah Income on Net Returns (NI) (H3)

Apart from that, fund distribution income can also come from Musyarakah fund distribution products. So it can be concluded that Musyarakah income obtained by sharia banks also has an influence on Net Returns (NI).

The statement above is also in line with studies that have been carried out previously Jati (2018), Tiyas (2020) and Awintasari & Nurhidayati (2021) which stated that the income obtained by Islamic banks can influence Net Returns. From several previous studies, it is known that there is an influence between the income generated by Sharia Banking and Net Returns. However, the income referred to here is Sharia Banking income as a whole. So it is not yet known specifically about the influence of Musyarakah Income on Net Returns.

Influence of Murabahah Income on Firm Size (H4)

As explained above, Firm Size can be influenced by the amount of profit or profits obtained by a company. Meanwhile, the profits of Islamic banks themselves can be obtained through income generated from an activity or activities carried out by Islamic banking. One of them is an activity in the form of Murabahah. So that the income generated from Murabahah activities (Murabahah Income) influences Firm Size. This is also in line with previous studies by Cahyani et al. (2024) and Wulandari (2020), which explained that the two have a positive relationship. However, no more specific explanation has been found regarding the influence of Murabahah Income on Firm Size.

Effect of Mudharabah Income on Firm Size (H5)

Apart from that, sharia banking profits can also be obtained through activities in the form of Mudharabah. So Mudharabah income also influences Firm Size. This is also in line with previous studies Cahyani et al. (2024) and Wulandari (2020), which show that the two have a relationship. However, no more specific explanation has been found regarding the influence of Mudharabah Income on Firm Size.

Influence of Musyarakah Income on Firm Size (H6)

Other sharia bank benefits can also be obtained through activities in the form of Musyarakah. So Musyarakah income also influences Firm Size. This is also in line with studies that have been conducted previously Cahyani et al. (2024) and Wulandari (2020), which state that the two have a relationship. However, no more specific explanation has been found regarding the influence of Musyarakah Income on Firm Size.

The Effect of Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah Income on Net Returns (NI) (H7)

From the first hypothesis (H1) to the third hypothesis (H3), a statement can be drawn that there is an influence between total Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah Income on Net Returns. And this is also in line with previous studies by Jati (2018), Tiyas (2020), and Awintasari & Nurhidayati (2021) which stated that the income earned by Islamic banks can influence Net Returns.

To better understand the relationship between variables which will be discussed in this journal, a description or scheme will be included regarding the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Here's the depiction:

Source: Data managed by the author

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

III. METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out using quantitative descriptive analysis by describing *real* (original) data in the form of numbers or numerical (quantitative) variables that have been collected (Sugiyono, 2014) from several *valid* sources (clear and correct) and using secondary data from five sharia banking companies in Indonesia as sample data. The five sharia banking companies include Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI), Bank Bukopin Syariah, BCA Syariah, and Bank Aceh Syariah. From the five sharia banks, data was taken in the form of murabahah income, mudharabah income, musyarakah income, net rewards and firm size. This data was obtained through the financial reports for 2018 quarter I to 2023 quarter III issued by the five sharia banking companies. From the results of collecting these five data, around 115 sample data were obtained which will be tested in this research.

Apart from that, the tests in this study also used panel data regression analysis and moderation regression analysis (MRA) as data analysis methods. The interaction test or MRA is an analytical method to maintain sample integrity and provide a basis for evaluating the influence of moderating variables known as (Ghozali, 2018).

Panel data regression analysis has the formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Net Rewards (NI)

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X₁ = Murabahah Income

X₂ = Mudharabah Income

X₃ = Musharaka Income

e_i = Error

Meanwhile, Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA) has the formula:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 Z + \beta_4 X_1 * Z + \beta_5 X_2 * Z + e$$

Where:

Y = Net Rewards (NI)

α = Constant

β = Regression Coefficient

X₁ = Murabahah Income

X₂ = Mudharabah Income

X₃ = Musharaka Income

Z = Firm Size

e_i = Error

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Research Results

Descriptive Analysis

Table 2
Statistics Descriptive

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	Y	Z
Mean	1074393.	28360.33	524801.7	4.289478	1700.652
Median	363988.0	15402.00	202520.0	4.580000	1708,000
Maximum	11354171	221513.0	4722223.	7.790000	1958,000
Minimum	13891.00	0.000000	23919.00	0.440000	1545,000
Std. Dev.	2067375.	37135.26	875018.6	2.200687	115.0835
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.019131	0.042586
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

The table above shows that the number of research samples used for the sharia banking sector was 115 samples for sharia banking in Indonesia for the period 2018.Q1-2023.Q3. Based on the results of the descriptive statistics above, the Murabah Income variable (X1) has the following values: average 1074393, median 363988.0, maximum 11354171, minimum 13891.00, and standard deviation 2067375.

Meanwhile, the Mudharabah Income variable (X2) has the following detailed values: the average is 28360.33, the median is 15402.00, the maximum value is 221513.0, the minimum value is 0.000000, and the standard deviation is 37135.26.

Meanwhile, the Musyarakah Income variable (X3) has the following detailed values: mean or average 524801.7, median 202520.0, maximum 4722223., minimum 23919.00, and standard deviation 875018.6.

Meanwhile, the Net Rewards (NI) (Y) variable has the following detailed values: mean or average 4.289478, median 4.580000, maximum 7.790000, minimum 0.440000, and standard deviation 2.200687.

Meanwhile, the Firm Size (Z) variable has the following detailed values: mean or average 1700.652, median 1708.000, maximum 1958.000, minimum 1545.000, and standard deviation 115.0835.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Models

Test Chow

The Chow test is carried out to determine the most optimal model, between the Common Effect Model (CEM) or the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 3
Test Chow

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F	67.693093	(4,107)	0.0000
Chi-square cross-section	145.068244	4	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

From the tests that have been carried out, the chi-square cross-section probability is 0.0000. This value is smaller than 0.05. Thus, the model that will be used because it is felt to be the best to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Hausman test

The Hausman test aims to find out which model is most suitable to use, between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 4
Hausman test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
Random cross-section	10.096317	3	0.0178

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

From the tests that have been carried out, it appears to produce a probability of 0.0178. This value is smaller than 0.05. Thus, the model that will be used because it is felt to be the best to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Table 5

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

Based on the graph above, it appears to produce a probability of 0.101291. This value is greater than 0.05. Thus it can be said that in this study the data used was normally distributed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 6
Multicollinearity Test

	X1	X2	X3
X1	1	0.71142970238855	0.9573507352249144
X2	0.71142970238855	1	0.787687481414479
X3	0.9573507352249144	0.787687481414479	1

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

From the tests that have been carried out, it appears that the correlation between variables is less than 0.85, except for variable X1 when it meets X3 whose value is greater than 0.85. This shows that there is multicollinearity between the independent variables in the research data.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 7
Heteroscedasticity Test

F-statistic	1.317322	Prob. F(9.105)	0.2368
Obs*R-squared	11.66761	Prob. Chi-Square(9)	0.2327
Scaled explained SS	6.214306	Prob. Chi-Square(9)	0.7183

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

From the tests that have been carried out, it appears that the Chi-Square Probability (Obs*R-squared) is 0.2327, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, it can be said that there is no indication or does not show the existence of heteroscedasticity in the regression model used in this research.

Panel Data Regression Analysis

As explained above, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM). So, the results of panel data regression analysis using the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) are as follows:

Table 8
Analysis Fixed Effect Model (FEM) Panel Data Regression

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	7.63E-07	1.91E-07	3.995761	0.0001
X2	-3.49E-06	3.73E-06	-0.936549	0.3511
X3	-1.39E-06	4.73E-07	-2.946080	0.0039
C	4.300212	0.111287	38.64068	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

MRA is a variable that can show how strong the relationship is between the independent variable and the dependent variable. This is the result of moderated regression analysis (MRA):

Table 9
Analysis Regression Moderation

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	1.35E-05	4.09E-06	3.311410	0.0013
X2	-3.08E-05	6.32E-05	-0.487544	0.6269
X3	-1.83E-05	1.07E-05	-1.702974	0.0916
X1Z	-7.12E-07	2.35E-07	-3.026527	0.0031
X2Z	1.56E-06	3.44E-06	0.452195	0.6521
X3Z	9.96E-07	6.07E-07	1.641252	0.1038
C	4.006845	0.159988	25.04461	0.0000

MSE Root	0.732329	R-squared	0.888291
Mean dependent var	4.289478	Adjusted R-squared	0.877550
SD dependent var	2.200687	SE of regression	0.770085
Akaike info criterion	2.406131	Sum squared resid	61.67517
Schwarz criterion	2.668689	Log likelihood	-127.3525
Hannan-Quinn Criter.	2.512702	F-statistic	
Durbin-Watson stat	0.880229	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

Statistical Test

T test

Carried out to test the differences between the dependent variable and the independent variable significantly. This test is also useful for measuring how big the influence is between each variable, whether the resulting value is below a significance of 0.05 or more than 0.05, besides that it can also be used to test and find out the truth of the hypothesis that has been proposed. To find out this, here are the test results:

Table 10
T test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X1	1.35E-05	4.09E-06	3.311410	0.0013
X2	-3.08E-05	6.32E-05	-0.487544	0.6269
X3	-1.83E-05	1.07E-05	-1.702974	0.0916
X1Z	-7.12E-07	2.35E-07	-3.026527	0.0031
X2Z	1.56E-06	3.44E-06	0.452195	0.6521
X3Z	9.96E-07	6.07E-07	1.641252	0.1038
C	4.006845	0.159988	25.04461	0.0000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

Based on the test results above, it is known that the results obtained can be described as follows:

1. Hypothesis 1 (H1): Murabahah income influences Net Returns (NI) with a coefficient of 1.35E-05 and a probability of 0.0013, which is smaller than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Murabahah Income influences Net Returns (NI) in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.
2. Hypothesis 2 (H2): Mudharabah income has no influence on Net Returns (NI) with a coefficient of -3.08E-05 and a probability of 0.6269 which is greater than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Mudharabah Income does not affect Net Benefits (NI) in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.
3. Hypothesis 3 (H3): Musyarakah Income has an influence on Net Returns (NI) with a coefficient of -1.83E-05 and a probability of 0.0916 which is smaller than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Musyarakah Income influences Net Income (NI) in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.
4. Hypothesis 4 (H4): Murabahah income influences Firm Size with a coefficient of -7.12E-07 and a probability of 0.0031 which is smaller than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Murabahah Income influences Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.
5. Hypothesis 5 (H5): Mudharabah income has no influence on Firm Size with a coefficient of 1.56E-06 and a probability of 0.6521 which is greater than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Mudharabah Income does not affect Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.
6. Hypothesis 6 (H6): Musyarakah Income has an influence on Firm Size with a coefficient of 9.96E-07 and a probability of 0.1038 which is smaller than the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This shows that Musyarakah Income influences Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period.

F test

This was done to identify the significant influence of independent variables (simultaneously) on the dependent variable. Using a significance value of 0.05 or 5%, provided that if the significance of F is less than 0.05, then the regression coefficient can be considered suitable for use. Following are the test results:

Table 11

F test

MSE Root	0.732329	R-squared	0.888291
Mean dependent var	4.289478	Adjusted R-squared	0.877550
SD dependent var	2.200687	SE of regression	0.770085

Akaike info criterion	2.406131	Sum squared resid	61.67517
Schwarz criterion	2.668689	Log likelihood	-127.3525
Hannan-Quinn Criter.	2.512702	F-statistic	82.69885
Durbin-Watson stat	0.880229	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

From this test, the F value is 0.000000, smaller than the significance value of 0.05 or 5%. It can be concluded that Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah income simultaneously influences Net Returns (NI).

Coefficient of Determination Test

Used to project the magnitude or significance of the contribution of the influence provided by the independent variable to the dependent variable.

Table 12
Coefficient Test determination

MSE Root	0.732329	R-squared	0.888291
Mean dependent var	4.289478	Adjusted R-squared	0.877550
SD dependent var	2.200687	SE of regression	0.770085
Akaike info criterion	2.406131	Sum squared resid	61.67517
Schwarz criterion	2.668689	Log likelihood	-127.3525
Hannan-Quinn Criter.	2.512702	F-statistic	82.69885
Durbin-Watson stat	0.880229	Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

Source: Eviews (Data managed by the author)

Based on the table above, it shows the Adjusted R-squared value is 0.877550. This shows that Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah income contributes 87.55% of the Net Returns (NI) variable, and the rest is in other variables outside the regression model.

Discussion of Theoretical Studies

The Effect of Murabahah Income on Net Returns

The results of the T test above produce the conclusion that Murabahah Income has an effect on Net Returns (NI). With a coefficient value of 1.35E-05 and a probability of 0.0013. This value is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. Thus, this value shows that Murabahah Income has an influence on Net Returns in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the first hypothesis (H1) stated above, namely that Murabahah Income has an effect on Net Returns (NI), can be accepted.

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on Net Returns

The results of the T Test above result in the conclusion that Mudharabah Income does not have a significant effect on Net Returns (NI). With a coefficient value of -3.08E-05 and a probability of 0.6269. This value is above the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.

This value shows that Mudharabah Income cannot strengthen its influence on Net Returns (NI). So the conclusion is that Mudharabah Income does not significantly influence Net Returns in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the second hypothesis (H2) stated above, namely that Mudharabah Income has an effect on Net Returns (NI), is rejected.

The Effect of Musharaka Income on Net Returns

From the results of the T Test, it is concluded that Musyarakah Income has an effect on Net Returns (NI). With a coefficient value of $-1.83E-05$ and a probability of 0.0916. This value is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This value shows that Musyarakah Income has an influence on Net Returns in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the third hypothesis (H3) stated above, namely that Musyarakah Income has an effect on Net Returns (NI), can be accepted.

The Effect of Murabahah Income on Firm Size

From the results of the T Test, it is concluded that Murabahah Income has an effect on Firm Size. With a coefficient value of $-7.12E-07$ and a probability of 0.0031. This value is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This value shows that Murabahah Income has an influence on Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the fourth hypothesis (H4) stated above, namely that Murabahah Income has an influence on Firm Size, can be accepted.

The Effect of Mudharabah Income on Firm Size

From the T Test results above, it shows that Mudharabah Income has no influence on Firm Size. By recording a coefficient value of $1.56E-06$ and a probability of 0.6521. This value is above the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This value shows that Mudharabah Income cannot strengthen its influence on Firm Size. So it can be concluded that Mudharabah Income has no influence on Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the fifth hypothesis (H5) stated above, namely that Mudharabah Income has an influence on Firm Size, is rejected.

The Influence of Musyarakah Income on Firm Size

From the results of the T Test, it is concluded that Musyarakah Income can influence Firm Size. By recording a coefficient value of $9.96E-07$ and a probability of 0.1038. This value is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%. This value shows that Musyarakah Income has an influence on Firm Size in the Sharia Banking sector for the 2018Q1-2023Q3 period. So the sixth hypothesis (H6) stated above, namely Musyarakah Income, has an influence on Firm Size is accepted.

The Effect of Murabahah, Mudharabah, and Musyarakah Income on Net Returns

The F test above uses a significance value of 0.05 or 5%, provided that if the F significance value is below or less than 0.05, it means that the regression coefficient is suitable for use. And from the F test results above, the F significance value is 0.000000, this value is below the significance value of 0.05. So, the conclusion is that there is a

simultaneous influence of Murabahah, Mudharabah and Musyarakah Income on Net Returns (NI) in the Sharia Banking sector for the period 2018Q1-2023Q3. So the seventh hypothesis (H7) which has been listed above, namely Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, and Musyarakah Income affecting Net Returns (NI) can be accepted.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

case below contains the results of research regarding the influence of Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, and Musyarakah Income on Net Returns and Firm Size which were discussed previously. The following are the important points that can be learned from the results of this research:

- 1) Murabahah Income has an influence on Net Returns, with a recorded probability of 0.0013. This statement projects that this figure is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 2) Mudharabah Income has no influence on Net Returns, with a recorded probability of 0.6269. This statement projects that this figure is above the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 3) Musyarakah Income has an influence on Net Returns, with a probability of 0.0916. This statement projects that this figure is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 4) Murabahah income has an influence on Firm Size, with a probability of 0.0031. This statement projects that this figure is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 5) Mudharabah income has no influence on Firm Size, with a probability of 0.6521. This statement projects that this figure is above the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 6) Musyarakah Income has an influence on Firm Size, with a probability of 0.1038. This statement projects that this figure is below the significance value of 0.5 or 5%.
- 7) Murabahah Income, Mudharabah Income, and Musyarakah Income, all three of which simultaneously have an influence on Net Returns, registering a significance of F 0.000000. This statement projects that this figure is below the significance value of 0.05 or 5%.

Suggestion

To future researchers, the author strongly recommends increasing the sample size in the next study or if there is further research. Because the addition of the sample will further expand the scope of the research, the results obtained will also be different from research in this journal. By using more data, the research results also have the potential to be more accurate compared to the research results in this journal.

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